

Diversification as a mechanism for developing and increasing enterprises' financial incomes in a knowledge-intensive and high-tech industrial complex

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Аннотация. Прогнозирование и оценка темпов развития, а также ожидаемых финансовых доходов предприятий наукоемкого и высокотехнологичного производственного комплекса является актуальной, важной и достаточно сложной научно-практической проблемой. Диверсификационные мероприятия, осуществляемые на данных предприятиях, повышают конкурентоспособность и инновационность производимой ими наукоемкой и высокотехнологичной продукции. В статье проанализированы существующие методы и модели прогнозирования деятельности предприятий, обоснован и разработан новый экономико-математический инструментарий. Он предназначен для оценки темпов развития и ожидаемых доходов предприятий, занятых развитием диверсификации производства. Предложенный инструментарий может применяться для решения различных прогнозных и экспертно-аналитических задач.

Abstract. Forecasting and assessing the pace of development, as well as the expected financial incomes of enterprises in a knowledge-intensive and high-tech industrial complex is an urgent, important, and rather complex scientific and practical problem. The diversification measures carried out at these enterprises increase the competitiveness and innovativeness of their knowledge-intensive and high-tech products. The article analyzes the existing methods and models of forecasting the activities of enterprises and substantiates and develops a new economic and mathematical toolkit designed to assess the pace of development and expected incomes of enterprises operating in a diversified environment. The proposed tools can be used to solve various predictive and expert-analytical tasks.

Ключевые слова: прогнозирование, экономико-математическое моделирование, авторегрессия, аддитивная модель, наукоемкое предприятия, диверсификация, производственный комплекс, финансовые доходы.

Keywords: forecasting, economic and mathematical modeling, autoregression, additive model, knowledge-intensive enterprises, diversification, production complex, financial income.

Introduction.

The task of forecasting and assessing the development pace of a knowledge-intensive and high-tech (KIHT) industrial complex, as well as the expected financial income, is one of the most important and most difficult tasks for planning the activities of an innovative enterprise. The solution to this problem is usually associated with the use of specific methods, models, and tools, which are considered in various scientific publications [2, 10, 15, 17, 18]. However, it must be borne in mind that the economic and mathematical approach to forecasting development and expected financial income does not have universality, and its effectiveness is determined by numerous and diverse factors and production conditions. For this reason, forecasting at KIHT enterprises, where volumes and types of production vary, differs significantly from methods of solving a similar problem for enterprises where financial flows

and production levels are distributed approximately equally over time.

Consideration of these circumstances in the activities of a knowledge-intensive enterprise should be carried out not only when planning financing processes but also when paying all types of taxes. It should also be remembered that the factor of changes in the volume of fabricated products should be taken into account in the methods of determining the correction coefficient of profitability not only of an individual enterprise but also of the entire KIHT complex, in which new integrated structures are being formed [13, 16]. Therefore, the discussed factor is of particular importance in forecasting and estimating the expected financial income and, as a result, plays a special role in making rational management decisions on the innovative development of a knowledge-intensive enterprise.

The uncertainty and riskiness for the production, financial, and scientific activities of KIHT enter-

prises in the international markets of knowledge-intensive goods and services [12, 14] have increased sharply in recent years due to the deterioration of the external economic situation, approximately the same as at the end of the last century [8, 9]. In the context of globalization, the political situation in the world has worsened and become more complicated, which negatively affects the foreign economic activity of knowledge-intensive enterprises, as well as the pace and effectiveness of their innovative development. Many organizational and economic measures taken by the state (financial assistance, lending, state support, import substitution, etc.) designed to reduce, minimize, and neutralize the negative consequences of these circumstances do not guarantee KIHT enterprises a successful transition to uniform, stable, and sustainable production progress. A decrease in the volume of innovative products for various purposes is observed in many knowledge-intensive enterprises due to currency fluctuations, sanctions, low profitability, lack of required financial resources, and other reasons. Taking into account the circumstances discussed above, the task of forecasting and estimating the expected financial income from the production activities of KIHT enterprises operating in conditions of decreasing volumes and changing types of high-tech products has acquired increased relevance and scientific and practical significance.

This task is especially relevant for KIHT enterprises, which, along with the factors listed above, are actively and positively influenced by the results of the diversification activities that they carry out. These measures make it possible to increase the competitiveness of the products produced by KIHT enterprises, as well as the effectiveness and validity of managing the main processes in their innovation activities [3, 4, 5, 6].

Special attention should be paid to significant changes in the volumes and types of goods and services produced by KIHT enterprises. Such changes are observed in this area during periods of active diversification. This factor must be taken into account, since it has a serious impact on the processes of developing and making strategic and tactical management decisions, the adequacy of which should be tightly linked to forecasting the expected financial and economic results of innovative production activities. Moreover, this form of forecasting should be based on the integrated and systematic use of not only qualitative but also economic, mathematical, and econometric (quantitative) models and methods.

Analysis and comparison of models and methods for forecasting financial and economic results of high-tech enterprises in conditions of changing volumes and types of products.

Among the large number of models designed and actively used to predict expected financial and economic results, trend-seasonal models, autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA model), as well as various types of adaptive models are widely used [1].

Currently, trend-seasonal models stand out among the most widely used predictive models that take into account the instability and seasonality of knowledge-intensive production. This type of model is based on the assumption that during the forecast time period, the main factors and main trends of the previous period will remain the same, or that changes in these factors and trends in the studied perspective can be identified in advance, scientifically justified, and taken into account in the forecasting process, i.e. the studied production processes have great inertia. The experience of using trend-seasonal models shows that, despite their simplicity, they are able to give reliable and accurate forecast results. A significant disadvantage of this type of models is their inability to take into account changes in the studied indicators in short time intervals. However, for medium- and long-term forecasting of knowledge-intensive enterprise results, this disadvantage becomes insignificant, since for such forecasting, the minimum time duration of the changes period is usually measured in years.

ARIMA models make it possible to make long-term and short-term forecasts for various time series. Some modifications of this type models make it possible to formalize time series very accurately, individual components of which may change. This type of predictive models is clearly and strictly mathematically formalized, which allows considering this model toolkit one of the most reasonable among the numerous predictive models. For some time, it was even believed that ARIMA models could be used to make the most accurate and detailed forecasts, since they are a successful generalization of many various models. However, under some changing external circumstances, the forecast obtained using these models turned out to be comparable in quality to the forecast constructed using exponential smoothing models. This led to the fact that scientists and practitioners stopped believing in the incomparable advantage of these models over others and made the logically correct conclusion that the most appropriate model for this problem should be used to solve each specific problem.

To successfully complete the procedure for constructing a qualitative ARIMA model, at least 40 separate observations must be made. At the same time, a sufficiently long time period is required to create and mathematically formalize a qualitative model of this type, and the developer analyst must have extensive scientific and practical experience. Thus, the development and application of ARIMA models for solving everyday scientific and practical problems turn out to be difficult and, moreover, require the use of additional specialized statistical tools.

Predictive adaptive models are based on the mathematical tools of exponential smoothing. Numerous and diverse modifications of this model toolkit have led to the creation of special predictive adaptive models that take into account the oscillatory component in the studied and analyzed time series. The Holt-Winters model and the Theil-Wage

model, which is Holt's sophisticated model, have become the most famous and widely used among models of this type [7, 19, 20].

The Holt-Winters model is developed on the basis of complementing the capabilities and advantages of the Holt linear growth model of a two-parameter type and useful forecasting features of the Winters model, which takes into account additive seasonality. The time series in the Holt-Winters model is represented as a combination of a linear trend with an imposed multiplicatively oscillatory component. The difference between the Theil-Wage model and the Holt-Winters model lies in its additivity. The development and use of this model type make it possible to simplify the forecasting process significantly, since the multiplicative model, which has the possibility of linear growth, turns out to be mathematically complex and not convenient to use. When building these two predictive models, a sequence of data consisting of at least 3 periods is required:

- according to the data of the initial period, the oscillatory coefficients are determined;
- the data of the next period are used to build a predictive additive model, but the oscillatory coefficients calculated in the initial period are used in an unadapted form;
- according to the data of the third (last) period, optimal smoothing constants are determined for the oscillatory component.

The problem of continuous smoothing seems to be quite difficult, because if it has oscillatory normalized coefficients, then it is necessary to solve a very complex nonlinear equation, and if non-normalized coefficients are used, then they cannot be calculated. In the same way, coefficients should be determined to build a high-quality trend component. All of the above indicates that the process of constructing predictive adaptive Holt-Winters and Theil-Wage models turns out to be very time-consuming, and specialized statistical tools are also required for their practical use.

Economic and mathematical tools for forecasting the pace of development and expected financial income of KIHT enterprises in a diversified environment.

Depending on the types of oscillatory changes, two main types of models are traditionally distinguished: additive and multiplicative models.

The additive model can be represented as follows:

$$m_t = w_t + r_t + f_t, \quad (1)$$

and the multiplicative model as:

$$m_t = w_t \times r_t \times f_t, \quad (2)$$

where w_t – oscillatory component;

r_t – trend component;

f_t – random component.

If the additive model (1) is used, it is assumed that the potential error determined by the random component has a normal distribution with constant variance and zero expectation.

$$f_t = N(0, d_f^2). \quad (3)$$

If the multiplicative model (2) is used, in which the error is taken into account not additively, but multiplicatively, then first this model must be

presented in an additive format using a logarithm, and then, by analogy with the model (1), assume:

$$\ln f_t = \ln N(0, d_f^2). \quad (4)$$

Then, in the multiplicative model (2), the error takes the form of a logarithmically normal distribution:

$$f_t = \log N(0, d_f^2). \quad (5)$$

If the error distribution turns out to be normal, then this circumstance becomes a formal criterion that makes it possible to check the adequacy of the selected type for the predictive model. The normal distribution, which was obtained after constructing a predictive model based on an empirical sequence of data, makes it possible to conclude that the model of the most appropriate type has been selected.

As noted above, the success and effectiveness of adaptive predictive models in a variety of practical activities and especially accurate and powerful, but at the same time complex tools based on ARIMA models largely depend on the analyst's qualifications and practical experience, and also require the use of additional specialized statistical software. The mentioned factors (qualified personnel and specialized software packages) are typical for large knowledge-intensive enterprises usually. These factors are very rare in medium-sized and small-sized KIHT enterprises. Therefore, trend-seasonal models are still used as the main predictive tools, which can be worked with by non-programming users using the capabilities of the MS Excel spreadsheet processor.

Currently, various algorithms for developing trend-seasonal models are used in practice. The following four main stages are present in a significant part of those models without taking into account the causes that generate oscillatory changes [11]:

- 1) identifying the presence of a trend in the time series;
- 2) identification of the presence of oscillatory changes in the time series;
- 3) filtering of the time series under study;
- 4) assessment of the adequacy and accuracy of the constructed predictive model.

The presence of a trend in the time series under study is usually determined by visual analysis of its graph. To strictly prove the presence of a trend in a time series, existing analytical methods should be applied, which make it possible to verify the assumption of the constancy for the average value in this time series.

To identify the presence of fluctuations in the time series under study, its visual analysis or strict analytical methods should also be used to check the randomness of the component remaining in the time series after the detected trend is isolated from it. This check is traditionally based either on calculating the indices of oscillatory changes and constructing the corresponding oscillatory wave, or on constructing a correlogram and determining the autocorrelation coefficients.

The studied time series in the filtering process should be divided into the three elements discussed above: the oscillatory component, the trend, and the random component. To perform such a separation, spectral and iterative methods should be used. Iterative methods that provide the required

filtering accuracy and do not have increased complexity are most often used for such separation.

Smoothing of the studied time series using the centered moving average method is performed at the initial stage of the filtration process.

At the second stage of the filtering process, a time series filtered from the trend is formed, in which only the oscillatory and various random components remain. The method of trend removal depends on the type of model used (multiplicative or additive) time series.

An additive time series model can be represented as a formula (6):

$$k_t = m_t - m_t^s, \quad (6)$$

where m_t^s is a smoothed time series at a point in time t .

The following formula is used for a multiplicative time series model (7):

$$k_t = m_t / m_t^s. \quad (7)$$

At the third stage of the filtration process, the calculated k_t values are averaged for each month (quarter) for all analyzed years.

The fourth stage of the filtration process is designed to determine the magnitude of the oscillatory component w_t .

Deseasonalization of the time series makes it possible to perform the filtration process at the fifth stage.

At the sixth stage of the filtering procedure, the approximating equation is determined using the least squares method for the calculated deseasonalized series. If the time t is sequentially inserted into this equation, then for the month (quarter) i the values of the trend r_{ij} can be determined in the year j .

At the seventh (final) stage of the time series filtering process, the values of the random component are calculated.

Using the model constructed in this way makes it possible to perform the required forecasting m_{ij}^p using formulas (8) and (9) for the month (quarter) i in the year j :

- for an additive time series model:

$$m_{ij}^p = r_{ij} + w_t, \quad (8)$$

- for a multiplicative model:

$$m_{ij}^p = r_{ij} \times w_t. \quad (9)$$

The proposed algorithm for the development of trend-seasonal forecast models is considered one of the most effective and can be successfully used in practical expert and analytical activities. However, numerous varieties of this algorithm, making it possible to take into account the peculiarities of its use in various specific conditions, can be developed and applied depending on the nature of the economic process under study, on the software and information tools available to the analyst, on the goals set, the type of forecast model used, and some other factors.

Improving the predictive tools for estimating the expected financial income of diversified KИHT enterprises.

Certain modifications that enhance the capabilities of existing standard calculation methods and take into account the features and functionality of tabular processors used by office analysts should be made in the algorithm for forming trend-seasonal models in order to improve and increase the accuracy of forecasting in economic and mathematical

tools that allow estimating the expected financial incomes of knowledge-intensive enterprises while diversifying their products for various purposes. This circumstance becomes especially important and practically significant for the application of the modified algorithm, since it makes it possible to reduce significantly the complexity of using computational procedures for nonlinear programming, statistics, and economic and mathematical modeling.

Further it is necessary to study the modified elements in more detail. It is advisable to apply the *F-criterion* for strictly analytical confirmation of the existence of oscillatory components in the time series under study. In the case of manual development of the discussed formation algorithm, the use of the *F-criterion* does not make it possible to obtain significant computational advantages compared to the traditional algorithm. However, when typical tabular processors are used, the computational procedure is significantly simplified due to the operation of the statistical functions available in these processors.

A distinctive feature of using the *F-criterion* is that this criterion is used for an analysis of a time series, the trend of which has already been deleted, that is, its use is carried out before the third stage of the filtering procedure discussed above. At the same time, it is assumed that there are no fluctuations in the time series filtered from the trend. If this assumption turns out to be correct, then the degrees of freedom of the *F-distribution* for the corresponding *F-statistics* will have the form $(T_0 - 1)$ and $(l - T_0)$, where for the studied time series T_0 is the oscillation period, and l is the number of observations.

The critical value of the *F-criterion* is usually calculated using built-in standard tabular statistical processors. For example, when using a typical MS Excel statistical processor, the following operation should be used for this calculation: F.INV.RT. If the value of the *F-criterion* exceeds a critical value, then this indicates that fluctuations are present in the analyzed time series.

The second modification is that for smoothing the time series under study, not the centered moving average method is used, but polynomial regression models, up to and including the third degree (in practice, a linear model is usually used – a polynomial of the 1st degree). The main advantage of this method is that all levels of the time series are used for smoothing, and when using a centered moving average, some levels are not processed, which especially negatively affects the accuracy of studying the “short” analyzed time series. If, for example, a centered moving average is used to study a time series with a duration of 2 years, with fluctuations with a frequency of 12 months, then 12 levels out of 24 will not be taken into account (levels 1–6 and 19–24 will be lost).

Another advantage of the smoothing process for the time series under study using a polynomial model is the ability not to perform the fourth stage of filtering.

In a typical MS Excel statistical processor, the “Add trendline” operation is an effective tool for developing two-factor polynomial models (up to and including the 6th degree). However, full automation of the forecasting process using this instrumental

method is impossible, since the regression equation does not appear on the worksheet, but on the diagram only. For this reason, it is advisable to use the "LINEST" operation to find the parameters of the regression equation required for forecasting.

The final modification of the typical smoothing algorithm is designed to filter the oscillatory component w_t by solving two optimization problems for additive or multiplicative models. Gradient search methods are traditionally used to solve these nonlinear programming problems. To increase the speed of convergence and accuracy of the calculation results, it is necessary to correctly determine the initial conditions, the length of each iteration, and the direction of the search.

The software component "Solver" of a typical MS Excel statistical processor implements an instrumental method for determining the generalized gradient. Numerous computational experiments have confirmed the fact that the procedure for finding the optimal values of the oscillatory component, as noted above, significantly depends on the accuracy of determining the initial conditions. To do this, it is recommended to use w_t values equal to the values averaged for each month (quarter) for all analyzed years k_t .

It may be assumed that optimization models significantly complicate the improved algorithm compared to the traditionally used algorithm for developing and formalizing trend-seasonal models. The available practical experience shows that this assumption turns out to be valid in the case of "manual" construction of such a predictive model. However, when using a typical MS Excel statistical processor and, in particular, its software component "Solver", solving optimization problems is simplified and does not require additional labor.

Conclusion.

In the process of carrying out this study, it is conceptually and mathematically justified that among the complex problems of planning the production activities of knowledge-intensive enterprises, one of the most important and practically significant is the task of predicting the expected financial income obtained through diversification activities. This type of activity makes it possible to produce innovative competitive products that are in demand in global and national markets.

The study and analysis of existing and widely used varieties of predictive tools have shown that there are currently no universal, effective, and accurate methods and approaches to assess the expected financial and economic results of diversified production activities. It is revealed that trend-seasonal models stand out among the forecast models actively used in practice, taking into account the instability and seasonality of knowledge-intensive production.

The economic and mathematical forecasting tools developed and presented in the article, based on modified trend-seasonal models, make it possible to predict accurately the amount of planned financial profit of knowledge-intensive enterprises engaged in diversification activities.

The proposed algorithm for constructing modern trend-seasonal forecast models is effective and can be successfully used to solve numerous

and diverse expert analytical and forecasting tasks. However, depending on the characteristics of the production process under study, the stationary software package available at the enterprise, the goals set for the management of the enterprise, and some other factors, varieties of this algorithm can be used to take into account the peculiarities of its use in various specific conditions.

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